

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Yangi taraqqiyot davrida oliy ta'lim tizimining rivojlanish tendensiyalari	10
Kirgizbayev Abdug'affor Karimjonovich	
Tebranma kimyoviy reaksiyalar mavzusini o'qitishning ahamiyati (Oksidlanish-qaytarilish reaksiyalari misolida).....	14
Artiqov Maqsud Bahodirovich, Sultanov Miribek Jabbarbergenovich, Bazarbayeva Laylo Gulmirza qizi	
Biologiya o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va metodlarning takomillashib borishi	17
Azimov Ibragimjon Toshpulatovich, Toshpulatova Nigina Ibrohimjon qizi, Toshpulatova Maftuna Ibrohimjon qizi	
Ta'lim jarayonida bulutli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning didaktik imkoniyatlari	22
Doniyorova Gulshan Toshmirzayevna	
Tarbiya – insoniyat rivojlanishining ajralmas qismi	27
Nayimova Aziza Dilmurot qizi	
Bolalarga xos psixologik o'zgarishlar va ularning yechimlari.....	31
Qodirova Malikaxon Kaxramonovna	
Tibbiy ma'lumotlarni avtomatlashtirish: ma'lumotlarni to'plash, qayta ishlash va tahlil qilish uchun modulli vositalar.....	36
Mamatov Maxtumquli Jumanazarovich, Rustamova Charosxon Rustamovna	
Lexicon Changes in the 21st Century Royal English.....	39
Sapayeva Yakutjan Maxmudovna	
Bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilari uchun ritmik gimnastika darslarini tuzilishi	45
Shaxbazova Gulrux Orifjon qizi, Xalilova Barnogul Abdulazizovna	
Maktabgacha 6–7 yoshli bolalarda bilish kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda multimedaning o'rni	49
Suvanova Nodirabegim Sadir qizi	
Физическое воспитание студенческой молодежи в современных условиях	53
Тангриев Абдукарим Товшович	
Tibbiyot instituti talabalarida professional tibbiy muloqot ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	57
Umarkulov Mukhtorali Islomkulovich	
Orqa miya shikastlanishida adaptiv jismoniy tarbiya vositalaridan foydalanish.....	60
Xalilova Barnogul Abdulazizovna, Shaxbazova Gulrux Orifjon qizi	
Творчества скотта туроу в оценке литературной критики	64
Хайдарова Умида Пулатовна	
Sport kurashi usullarini tasnifi, tizimi va ularning atamasi	69
A. R. Xodjanov	
Роль образования в реабилитации и реинтеграции детей-репатриантов	73
Юлдашев Санжар Рузимуродович	
O'quvchilarda liderlik xislatlarini shakllanishining gender jihatlarini.....	78
Yuldasheva Sevvara Ruzimurodovna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni partisipativ tayyorlashda ijtimoiy-perseptiv ko'nikmalarning ahamiyati	81
Muradova Maftuna Komilovna	
Sport kurashi usullarining tasnifi, tizimi va ularning atamasi	84
Faxriddin Karimov	
Yuqori sinflarda ingliz tili darslarida grammatik interferensiyani aniqlash va uni bartaraf etish usullari.....	88
Amirqulova Dilnoza Bahriddin qizi	
Pedagogik ta'lim innovatsion klasteri yondashuvi asosida bo'lajak mutaxassislarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	91
Baybayeva Muxayyo Xudaybergenovna, Zulxaydarov Javlonbek Abdukaxor o'g'li	
The Role of Non-Governmental Higher Education Institutions in Contemporary Educational Systems and their Economic Impact.....	94
I. Imomov	

Ingliz tilini o'rganishda autentik materiallardan foydalanish metodikasini takomillashtirish modeli	100
<i>Ismatova Madina Inomjon qizi</i>	
Elektron darsliklardan samarali foydalanish uchun qo'yilgan talablarning asosiy mezonlari.....	103
<i>Jumanov Xudoyor Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
Xorijiy tajribalar asosida ta'lim sifatini boshqarishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	106
<i>Karimova Maxbuba Mukimjonovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim talabalarida "health care" tafakkurini shakllantirishning pedagogik zaruriyati.....	109
<i>Mattiyev Ilhom Begmatdulobovich</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarining boshqaruvida jamoa motivatsiyasini oshirishdagi rahbarning roli.....	113
<i>Mirzayeva Faroxat Odiljonovna, Shukurova Shaxzodaxon Xolbek qizi</i>	
Yangi o'zbekiston taraqqiyot davrida tarbiyaviy texnologiyalar asosida yuksak ma'naviyatli shaxsni shakllantirish.....	116
<i>Nigmanova Umidaxon Baxodirxon qizi, Quvondiqova Dildora Komiljonovna</i>	
Oilaviy va axloqiy qadriyatlarni tarbiyalashda oila va maktab hamkorligi – pedagogik muammo	121
<i>Saidova Barno Narzullayevna</i>	
Talaba-yoshlarda reproduktiv salomatlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari va imkoniyatlari..	125
<i>Shodmonova Shoira Saidovna, Shodmonova Dilsora Shokirovna</i>	
Futbol ko'nikmalarini etnosport elementlari asosida shakllantirish.....	129
<i>Toshpo'latov Sirojjon Komiljon o'g'li</i>	
Abdulla Avloniy pedagogik merosida yoshlar ekologik tafakkurini rivojlantirish g'oyalari	132
<i>Umarova Malika Xisabidinovna</i>	
Umumta'lim muassasalarida – ta'lim sifatini boshqarish ustuvor yo'nalish sifatida	137
<i>Yakubova Muxtaram Abdumavlyanovna</i>	
Использование современных педагогических технологий на занятиях иностранного языка	140
<i>Виктория Мамаджанова</i>	
Открытое занятие физкультурный досуг "Колобок"	144
<i>Кинжабаева Дильбар Абдурафиковна</i>	
Толерантность у учителей: значение, роль и пути формирования.....	147
<i>Уразова М.Б., Бекбосынова З.К.</i>	
Ingliz tilini o'qitishda o'qish ko'nikmasini o'rgatishning an'anaviy va zamonaviy turlari talqini.....	153
<i>O'rinova Durdona Farhodovna</i>	
Deontologik yondashuv asosida maktab boshqaruvining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	156
<i>Abdulxayeva Moxiraxon Borixonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni milliy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiyalashning ahamiyati.....	160
<i>Ataniyazova O'g'iljan Rajapbayevna</i>	
O'quvchilarning neyropedagogik xususiyatlarini diagnostika qilish	163
<i>Babakulova Dilnoza Ramazonovna</i>	
Kasbiy ijtimoiylashuv – bo'lajak o'qituvchi huquqiy ijtimoiylashtirishning asosiy omili sifatida	167
<i>Ibotov Javohir Ulug'bekovich</i>	
Maktab direktorining boshqaruv faoliyatida qarorlarni qabul qilishda tavakkalchilikni boshqarish	170
<i>Jabborova Yulduzxon Hasan qizi</i>	
10-11-sinf o'quvchilarining biologiya fanini o'rganishda innovatsion fikrlash ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishning amaldagi holati.....	173
<i>Sharipova Aziza Mustafayevna</i>	
Bolalardagi inqiroz va uning sabablari.....	176
<i>Xasanova Iroda Alimjonovna</i>	
O'zbek adabiyotida modernizm va postmodernizm unsurlari	181
<i>Yuldasheva Dilnoza Bekmurodovna</i>	
"Taym menejment" ko'nikmalari asosida o'quvchilar vaqtini samarali boshqarish imkoniyatlarini shakllantirish	184
<i>Yuldasheva X.Q.</i>	

Динамика психологического благополучия личности студентов-психологов.....	191
Тиллашайхова Хосият Азаматовна	
Markaziy Osiyo tilshunosligining rivojlanish bosqichlari	194
Abdiminova Dildora Oybekovna	
Autizm spektrida buzilish aniqlangan bolalar ta'lim-tarbiyasida ota-onalarning roli.....	198
Alimova Gulchehra Qobilovna	
Autizm spektrida buzilish aniqlangan bolalarning ijtimoiy hayotdagi o'rnini	201
Asraxonova E'tibor Abduvaxob qizi	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kasbiy mahoratni shakllantirish texnologiyasi	206
G'iyasova Nargiza Yunus qizi	
Is'hoqxon to'ra ibrat asarlari asosida talabalarni pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash	210
Mirzayeva Faroxat Odiljonovna, Jo'rayeva Sitora Eshqobil qizi	
Pedagogik dasturiy vositalarni yaratishda ranglar tizimidan foydalanish	214
Mamanazarov Baxrom Jumonovich	
Solving Specific Problems With Specific Methodological Approaches	218
Muxammedova Nafisa Kamolovna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining raqamli kompetentligini oshirish masalalari va ularning yechimlari	223
Raxmatova Hamida Ismatillo qizi	
Integratsiyalashgan musiqa mashg'ulotlari jarayonida musiqiy idrokni shakllantirishga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim metodlari.....	227
Ruziyeva Orzigul Ilyosovna	
XXI asrda tasavvufning ma'naviy-tarbiyaviy jihatlari.....	230
Quvonov Sardor Zokirovich	
Mirzo Ulug'bekning pedagogik g'oyalari va uning ta'lim rivojidagi xizmatlari.....	233
Soatova Rayxona Sadridin qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyotning ta'lim sifatiga ijobiy ta'sirlari	236
To'rabekov Farxod Sanakulovich	
Umumta'lim maktabi 5-6-sinf o'qituvchilarini jismoniy tarbiyaga o'qitishda ilmiy-pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish nazariy asoslari	240
Toshtemirov Bekzod Faxriddin o'g'li	
Tarbiya nazariyasiga doir ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar va raqamli dunyoda tarbiya masalalarining nazariy-metodik asoslari.....	244
Yusupova Mahliyo Abdimin qizi	
Использование современных педагогических технологий на занятиях иностранного языка	248
Виктория Мамаджанова	
Использование аутентичных материалов в преподавании русского языка: преимущества и недостатки	252
Умаров Азиз Авазович	
O'qituvchilarda kasbiy identifikatsiyani rivojlantirish: tamoyillar, yondashuvlar va amaliy tajribalar.....	256
Abdusamiyev Dilmurod Abdug'ani o'g'li	
Kasbiy-pedagogik kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari	260
Abrorxonova Kamolaxon Abrorxon qizi	
Basketbolchilar uchun reabilitatsiya usullari va jarohatlarning oldini olish strategiyalari	263
Suyunov Tohir Nomoz o'g'li	
Yosh dzyudochilarni tayyorlashda innovatsion usullar: pedagogik va psixologik yondashuvlar.....	267
Husanov G'aybulla Usmanovich	
Maktabgacha ta'lim sohasida pedagog olimlarning milliy qadriyatlar asosida ekologik tarbiya berishga oid qarashlari.....	271
Ergasheva Umriniso Komilovna	
Nurota tog' tizmasining tabiiy geografik xususiyatlari.....	275
Esanqulova Dilbar Sayitovna	

Teacher's motivational management strategies for innovative activities	279
Egamberdiev Farkhod Botirovich	
Futboldagi psixologik trening: stressga bardoshlilikni oshirish usullari.....	283
Davronov Ernazar Orziyevich	
Yosh o'qituvchilar faoliyatida pedagogik qiyinchiliklar va ularni bartaraf etishning psixologik asoslari.....	287
Jumanova Nasiba Sherbojevna	
Tarbiyasi og'ir bolalarni ijtimoiylashtirishda oila, mahalla va maktab hamkorligi ishlari samaradorligining mazmuni.....	290
Kamolova Shirinoy Usarovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish savodxonligi darslarida sharq mutafakkirlarining ma'naviy merosidan foydalanishning samaradorligi	294
Maxmudova Muhlisa Abdilaziz qizi	
Ta'lim boshqaruvida maktab ta'limi tizimi statistikasini shakllantirish zaruriyati.....	297
Muradov Ikrom Turdiboyevich	
Using Movement Games in Teaching English in Preschools	301
Nishonova Ra'nokhon Abdullojon qizi	
The Role and Opportunities of Using Modern Methods in Improving Geographic Knowledge Among School Students.....	304
Ortiqova Iqbol Olimboyevna	
O'quvchilarni kasb-hunarga yo'naltirishda sharq allomalarining ma'naviy merosidan foydalanishning psixologik asoslari	310
Qarshiboeva Dilfuza Burliyevna	
O'quv faoliyati samaradorligiga ta'sir qiluvchi emotsional intellektni rivojlantirishning psixologik asoslari	314
Sangirova Nilufar	
Futbolda texnik va taktik tayyorgarlikning yosh futbolchilar rivojlanishiga ta'siri.....	317
Sultonov Vaxob Murotovich	
Ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishda ota-onalar bilan muloqot imkoniyatlaridan foydalanishning ilmiy asoslari.....	321
Toshpo'latova Nodira Xudjamurodovna	
O'smirlarda kuzatiladigan serzardalikning kelib chiqishi va korreksiyasi.....	325
Tuxtayeva Maxliyo Shamsiddinovna	
Yosh voleybolchilar uchun psixologik tayyorgarlikning o'yin samaradorligiga ta'siri.....	329
Suyunov Tohir Nomoz o'g'li	
Leveraging Global Economic Trends to Enhance English Language Education: A Methodological Approach for Economics Students	333
Z. Xasanova	
Некоторые семантические характеристики французских и узбекских антропонимов	336
Камолова Санобар Джаббаровна	
Стратегии подготовки специалистов для инклюзивного образования в Республике Казахстан (Опыт КазНУ)	340
Магайова А. С.	
Проектирование современной образовательной среды школы на основе художественного метода .	346
Рузметова Хилола Абдушориповна	
Inklyuziv ta'lim jarayonidagi boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini kollaborativ yondashuv asosida milliy tarbiyalashning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari.....	352
Ergashev Jahongir Mamanazarovich	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning deontologik xususiyatlarini shakllantirishning psixologik asoslari	357
Ahmedova Nasiba Achilovna	
Ilk bolalik davrining psixologik xususiyatlari.....	361
Askarova Nafisa Avazovna	
Oila – yoshlarni chet tillarni o'rganish jarayoniga ta'sir etuvchi ijtimoiy institut sifatida.....	365
Atamuxamedova Ra'no Fazildjanovna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Ilon obrazi qadimgi sharq xalqlari moddiy madaniyatida aks etishi 368 <i>Choriyeva Sedona Sharif qizi</i>
	Organization of Sports and Wellness Activities in Higher Educational Institutions 373 <i>Dehkonova Mahmuda Ortigovna</i>
	Xorijiy tajribalar asosida tarbiya jarayoni samaradorligini oshirish 376 <i>Farsaxonova Dilafruz Rizaxonovna</i>
	O'zbekistondagi kichik biznes subyektlarini banklar orqali moliyaviy rag'batlantirishning samaradorligini tahlil qilish va baholash 379 <i>Hamroqulov Xushbaxt Sadriddinovich</i>
	"Forsayt" texnologiyalari tarixi va undan sport ta'limida foydalanish imkoniyatlari 382 <i>Hayitov Oybek Eshboyevich</i>
	Fitonimlarning etimologik va leksik-semantik xususiyatlari (fransuz va o'zbek tillari misolida)..... 386 <i>Jumashova Sayyora Shonazarovna</i>
	Harakatli o'yinlarning tarixi, turkumlari va pedagogik ahamiyati 390 <i>Kulboyev Nodirjon Salaydinovich</i>
	Texnologiya darslarida STEAM ta'lim yondashuvi asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kreativlik qobiliyatini rivojlantirish 393 <i>Kulboyeva Dilnoza Abdug'ofurovna</i>
	O'smirlarda agressiv xulq-atvorning namoyon bo'lishi va uni bartaraf etish mexanizmlari..... 396 <i>M. S. Usmonova</i>
	Bo'lajak pedagoglarda STEAM ta'limini joriy etishning nazariy asoslari va ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyati..... 400 <i>Nurullayeva Ugulxon Ergashboyevna</i>
	Kurashchilarning musobaqa oldi texnik-taktik tayyorgarligi 405 <i>Ochilov Elbek Olimovich</i>
	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti metodistining murakkab va ko'p qirrali bo'lgan vazifalari 408 <i>Otaxanova Manzura G'ofurovna, Jo'rayeva Saida</i>
	Kognitiv pedagogika – o'quvchilarning aqliy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish omili 412 <i>Qabulov Baxrom Quzibayevich</i>
	Badiiy matnda o'ziniki bo'lmagan ko'chirma gaplarning uslubiy vazifalari..... 418 <i>Siddiqova Shoxida Isoqovna</i>
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarining badiiy va obrazli iste'dodini media ta'lim orqali rivojlantirish..... 422 <i>Xalillayeva Go'zaloy Mo'minjon qizi</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini ijodiy faoliyatga tayyorlash texnologiyasini tashkil etishning pedagogik asoslari 426 <i>Yusupova Sanobar Odil qizi</i>
	O'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlashini shakllantirish maqsadida masalalar sistemasini tanlash texnologiyalari 431 <i>Zokirov Furqat Muxsinovich</i>
	Эффективность использования ИКТ в контроле учебных достижений в старших классах образовательной школы 437 <i>Уразова М. Б., Асанова К. У.</i>
	Проблемы преподавания русского языка в вузах Узбекистана 441 <i>Норбоева Дилафруза Джумакуловна</i>
	Социальные особенности семей, воспитывающих детей с интеллектуальными нарушениями 444 <i>Пирманова Бахора Эшмухаммедовна</i>
	Geymifikatsiyadan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilar motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati 449 <i>Xaitova Nazokat</i>
	Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida o'quvchi yoshlar 453 <i>Norboyeva Ra'no Abrayevna</i>
	Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida o'quvchi yoshlar 453 <i>Norboyeva Ra'no Abrayevna</i>

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda steam texnologiyasidan foydalanish.....	456
Maxmutazimova Yulduz Raxmatovna	
Мaktabгача та'limda bolaning kitovxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishda oila bilan hamkorlikning ahamiyati.....	461
Jo'rayeva Nargiza Tairovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida pedagogning innovatsion faoliyati	465
Rizayeva Xusniya Ubayevna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida tasviriy faoliyatga o'rgatish usullari va metodlari	469
Choriyeva Durdona Anvarovna	
Qisqa muddatli guruhlar o'quv tarbiyaviy jarayonida ota-onalar bilan hamkorlik.....	474
Kasimova Dilrabo Bahadirovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti pedagoglarining kreativ qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish usullari	479
Maxmudova Durdona Mirkarimovna	
Современные подходы к экологическому воспитанию дошкольников.....	483
Ким Ирина Николаевна	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning kreativ kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi.....	486
Ziyayeva Umidaxon To'raxodjayevna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda bilishga qiziqishni shakllantirish mexanizmi.....	490
Kayumova Nargiza Mirziyatovna	
Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti tarbiyachilarining kreativ fikrlash qobiliyatini landshaft dizayni vositasida rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	494
Radjapova Zuxra Tirkashevna	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda kitobxonlik madaniyatini tarbiyalashning dolzarbligi va zaruriyati ..	498
Ochilova Xilola Sheraliyevna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti direktorlarini jamoa boshqaruvida kasbiy sifatlarni shakllantirish imkoniyatlari	502
Abdiyeva Fazilat Fayzulla qizi	
Psixodiagnostika – fan va amaliy faoliyat sifatida.....	506
Alixodjayeva Gulbahor Sobirovna	
Психологические основы успешного обучения: от мотивации до контроля	509
Терехова Ольга Евгеньевна	
Main Ways and Methods of Forming Students' Reflective Skills in the Process of Professional and Pedagogical Training	514
Ravshanova Nargiza Norboyevna	
Зарубежный опыт в применении STEAM технологий в дошкольном образовании.....	517
Садикова Д. Х.	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti tarbiyachilarining ota-onalar bilan hamkorlik faoliyati samaradorligi	520
Kamalova Gavhar Akbarovna	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni kasbiy pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash	524
Artikbayeva Aziza Abror qizi	
Fan va tabiatni tanishtirish orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni intellektual imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirish.....	527
Musulmonova Shahnoza To'lqinovna	
Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning kasbga qiziqishlarini rivojlantirish	531
Isabekova Dilafuz Shermirzayevna	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning kasbiy metodik kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning ahamiyati	536
Sultonsaidova Mushtariy Abzalxonovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan o'quv-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil etish	540
Nurbayeva Inobat To'likinovna	
Milliy hunarmandchilik asosida talabalarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashni takomillashtirish tamoyillari.....	544
Sharipova Guzal Sodiqovna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Tarbiya darslarida o'quvchilarning iqtisodiy savodxonligini oshirish: asosiy yondashuvlar va strategiyalar..... 550 Abdullayeva Zamiraxon Erkinboyevna
	Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining AKT kompetentligini shakllantirish..... 553 Askarova Zilolaxon Nurmuxamadovna
	Servis xizmati yo'nalishini o'qitishda kreativ yondashuv va uning samaradorligini oshirish strategiyalari.... 557 Barataliyeva Nasiba Mahmaminovna
	Taxminlarga asoslangan geografiya-tabiiy fanlarni o'qitish negizida 561 Djumayeva Moxigul Mamanazarovna
	Inklyuziv ta'lim sohasida tarbiyachi pedagoglarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini shakllantirish yo'llari 566 Djurakulova Lola Raxmonberdiyevna
	Raqamli madaniyat va uning sotsializatsiya jarayoniga ta'siri 569 Fayzullaeva Nilufar Sadullaevna
	The Factors that Influence Pronunciation in a Foreign Language..... 573 Isamutdinova Durdona Maripfjanovna
	Ta'limda iqtisodiy dunyoqarashni rivojlantirishda iqtisodiy ta'limotlar tarixi va taraqqiyoti 576 Jumanov Xayitmurot Toshniyozovich
	Raqamli ta'lim muhitini transformatsiyalash jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy moslashuvchanligini takomillashtirish shartlari 582 Li Natalya Aleksandrovna
	Boshlang'ich ta'limda to'plamlar va ular ustida amallarni bajarish xususiyatlari..... 586 Mavlonov Anvar O'ktamovich
	Ta'lim muassasasi rahbar xodimlarining ma'naviy qiyofasini forsait texnologiyasi orqali shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari 591 Nuriyeva Umida Buribayevna
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining texnologiya darslarida mustaqil faoliyat ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish 594 Rizakulov Shuhrat Xamrakulovich
	Qadimgi Xorazmning yirik badiiy markazi Xiva hunarmandchiligining rivojlanish tarixi 599 S. S. Safasheva, Radjapova Zuxra Tirkashevna
	Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning o'quvchilar ijodiy salohiyatining rivojlanishidagi o'rni..... 603 Xaydarova Sanobar
	Zamonaviy yoshlarda oilaviy qadriyatlar haqidagi tasavvurlar inqirozi 606 Shodiyeva Nodira Normamatovna
	Turkistonda jadidchilik harakatining vujudga kelishi va jadidlarning faoliyati..... 610 Tangirov Abduhamid, Matkarimova Nafisa
	Kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirish yo'llari 614 Urakova Zilola Salomovna
	The Intelligent Storytelling Method in Primary Education 617 Usmanov Abdijabbar Norbotayevich
	Формирование конструктивных копинг-стратегий у обучающейся молодежи 619 Аскарова Гулрух Оринбасаровна
	Сравнительное изучение падежной системы русского и узбекского языков 626 Джалилова Мунира Рахматовна
	Инклюзивное образование в рамках преподавания русского языка 628 Дилфуза Маърупова
	Методика развития когнитивных компетенций учащихся на уроках французского языка 632 Мирбобоева Дилфуза Бахтиёрвна
	O'quv jarayonini leksikografik ta'minlash mezonlari 635 Murodova U. D.

THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE PRONUNCIATION IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Isamutdinova Durdona Maripfjanovna

Teacher of the Department of German Language Theory and Practice of Andijan state institute of foreign languages

Abstract: The article discusses the various factors that influence children's language development and pronunciation. It explains how children acquire language during their early years of life and the role of observation, imitation, and interaction with caregivers in this process.

Key words: Language comprehension, pronunciation, speech disorders, language development

Annotatsiya: Maqolada bolalarning til rivojlanishi va talaffuziga ta'sir qiluvchi turli omillar tahlil etiladi. Unda bolalarning hayotining ilk yillarida tilni qanday o'rganishi, shuningdek, kuzatish, taqlid qilish va ota-onalar va vasiylar bilan o'zaro muloqotning bu jarayondagi o'rni tushuntiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tilni tushunish, talaffuz, nutq nuqsonlari, til rivojlanishi.

Аннотация: Статья обсуждает различные факторы, влияющие на развитие речи и произношение у детей. В ней объясняется, как дети учат язык в первые годы жизни, а также роль наблюдения, подражания и взаимодействия с родителями и опекунами в этом процессе.

Ключевые слова: Понимание языка, произношение, нарушения речи, развитие языка

INTRODUCTION

Language acquisition is a fascinating and intricate process, especially in the early years of life. Children typically begin decoding language through observation and interaction with their environment, learning through mimicry and trial and error. However, despite the apparent simplicity of this process, many children encounter language development challenges, including pronunciation difficulties. This article explores the factors influencing pronunciation in foreign language acquisition, focusing on various stages of language development and common speech disorders that can affect children.

It is truly remarkable how a child deciphers the secret of language during the first three to four years of life. From their initial cries to forming complete sentences, children undergo various developmental stages, at the end of which language becomes their primary tool for communication. Conversations with trusted caregivers—parents, siblings, and grandparents—form the most crucial framework for this process.

Children learn to speak by observing their surroundings and enhancing their linguistic competence through keen observation, imitation, and experimentation. However, while this may seem straightforward, the process is often complex. Unfortunately, recent school entry examinations have revealed that many students exhibit linguistic deficits. Alongside a limited vocabulary, a lack of basic terms, poor auditory memory, and incorrect sentence structures, children are increasingly showing signs of speech disorders.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pronunciation in a foreign language is influenced by various cognitive, linguistic, and social factors. Researchers in linguistics and second language acquisition have explored these factors to understand the complexities of pronunciation learning.

Lundquist-Meg (2015) emphasizes the role of early exposure to phonetic patterns, stating that children who are exposed to multiple languages at a young age develop better pronunciation due to increased phonological

awareness. Schart and Legutke (2012) highlight the significance of teacher competence and structured instruction in pronunciation development, arguing that explicit phonetic training can improve learners' articulation.

Balweg et al. (2014) discuss the impact of first language interference, noting that learners often transfer phonological rules from their native language, which can lead to difficulties in producing certain sounds. This is further supported by Isamutdinova (2024), who examines innovative pedagogical technologies and suggests that immersive and interactive methods, such as phonetic drills and shadowing techniques, can enhance pronunciation accuracy.

Durdona (2024) explores the role of social interaction in pronunciation learning, asserting that frequent communication with native speakers significantly improves phonetic skills by providing authentic input and corrective feedback. Similarly, Maxamadaliyevna (2024) discusses the influence of cultural background on pronunciation, noting that familiarity with the phonetic system of a target language's culture facilitates better articulation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article examines existing literature on language development, specifically focusing on pronunciation and speech disorders in children. The data was gathered from studies in developmental psychology, linguistics research, and educational materials discussing language acquisition and speech disorders. The primary objective was to identify key factors influencing pronunciation in foreign languages and the role of early language interactions in shaping pronunciation skills.

Why Learning to Speak Is Complicated? Although language learning is a highly complex process, it often appears to happen effortlessly. However, several prerequisites must be met for a child to develop speech. The child must be able to hear and see, process stimuli in the brain, and control the muscles involved in speech production. Additionally, children need frequent verbal interactions with caregivers and other speakers to learn essential language components, such as object names, descriptive properties, and proper sentence structure. Most parents instinctively provide the necessary linguistic input to facilitate language development. Every child learns at their own pace, leading to variations in speech development timelines. While these differences are not always a cause for concern, certain developmental benchmarks indicate when linguistic abilities should emerge. For example, a toddler saying, "Mama Lade," to mean "Mom, I'd like another piece of chocolate," is developmentally appropriate. However, if a preschooler continues to express desires in this manner, it may indicate a significant delay in language development ^[1].

Types of Speech and Language Disorders. Speech and language disorders can manifest in various ways, including difficulties with pronunciation (challenges in articulating sounds correctly), language comprehension (difficulty understanding spoken language), vocabulary (limited word knowledge or difficulty recalling words), and sentence structure and grammar (struggles with forming grammatically correct sentences).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results highlight several key factors influencing pronunciation in foreign language acquisition. Pronunciation errors are common in the early stages of language development. As children grow, they gradually master the sounds of their native language, with more complex sounds (such as "s," "z," and "r") becoming easier to articulate over time. Pronunciation disorders are among the most common speech-related issues in children. These disorders often involve mispronunciations or omissions of sounds, which may persist if not properly addressed. Common examples include substituting "r" with "l" or omitting sounds like "s" in words. Children with limited vocabulary often struggle with accurate pronunciation. As their vocabulary expands, they typically gain better control over pronunciation. Additionally, poor language comprehension can hinder a child's ability to use words correctly, thereby affecting pronunciation. The child's environment, particularly the frequency and quality of interactions with caregivers, plays a crucial role in language development. Children who are frequently exposed to rich, clear speech tend to develop better pronunciation skills.

Some children regularly substitute certain sounds with others, such as saying "l" instead of "r." These pronunciation errors are normal in early speech development but should be addressed if they persist into kindergarten age.

Research indicates that pronunciation development in children is influenced by biological, environmental, and social factors. Early language exposure, particularly through regular communication with caregivers and others, plays a crucial role in shaping correct pronunciation. However, persistent pronunciation errors may indicate underlying speech disorders, such as dyslexia or dysgraphia, and require attention.

Targeted interventions can significantly improve pronunciation. Speech exercises and pronunciation activities help children correct early mispronunciations. Additionally, vocabulary expansion and grammatical accu-

racy indirectly enhance pronunciation, as children articulate words more precisely when they understand their meanings and structures.

Parents and educators play a vital role in supporting pronunciation development by encouraging clear, slow speech, providing positive reinforcement, and avoiding criticism of mispronunciations. If pronunciation difficulties persist, consulting a speech therapist can help determine whether further intervention is necessary.

Sentence Structure and Grammar. Children affected by speech disorders fail to apply grammatical rules correctly, a condition referred to as dysgrammatism. They may omit words or entire parts of sentences, form plurals (“the dogs”) or past tense (“I hung on the bar”) incorrectly, confuse masculine and feminine forms (“the house”), use incorrect word endings (“you goes to school”), or ignore the proper word order in a sentence. Do not let pronunciation errors become the main focus of your conversations with your child. Pay attention to what your child is telling you; how they say it is less important. Consult a speech therapist if you are unsure whether your child’s speech development is appropriate ^[3].

How Can I Help My Child? Regardless of the type of language difficulty your child faces, there are several things you can do in everyday interactions to support them: Speak slowly to your child and maintain eye contact so they can observe correct pronunciation. Do not laugh at, scold, or criticize your child for making mistakes—this will only frustrate them. Praise your child for pronouncing sounds, words, and sentences correctly. Keep in mind that the content of what they say should be the primary focus. If you only pay attention to speech errors or correctly spoken words, your child may feel that the actual message is not important to you. You can best help your child by repeating their statements with the correct pronunciation or formulation, or by asking questions in the proper form. For example, if your child says, “das große Baum” (“the big tree”), you might respond with, “Yes, there’s a big tree. And over there, there are many small trees.” This way, your child learns the correct phrasing without feeling like they made a mistake. You can help expand your child’s vocabulary by looking at picture books together and discussing them, naming objects during games like Memory, or simply observing and talking about things around you. Talk to your child about their experiences, helping them structure their stories through appropriate questions and summaries so that others can understand them ^[4].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In summary, the role of teachers today is significantly more complex than it was a few decades ago. They are no longer merely transmitters of knowledge but also serve as learning companions, value educators, and social integrators. Teachers must navigate an increasingly digital world while simultaneously addressing the diverse needs of their students. The demands placed on them are high, yet the opportunities within this profession are equally vast. A modern teacher plays a crucial role in shaping a just and future-oriented society by not only imparting knowledge but also fostering the personal, social, and digital competencies of the next generation.

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Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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